

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D3.1 REQUIREMENTS AND ARCHITECTURE FOR CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING IN 6G

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D3.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Computing in 6G

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
6G	<i>The sixth-generation</i>
AES	<i>Advanced Encryption Standard</i>
AI	<i>Artificial intelligence</i>
AMD	<i>Advanced Micro Devices</i>
API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
ARM	<i>Advanced RISC Machine</i>
ASP	<i>AMD Secure Processor</i>
AWS	<i>Amazon Web Services</i>
CC	<i>Confidential Computing</i>
CPU	<i>Central Processing Unit</i>
DP	<i>Differential Privacy</i>
EPC	<i>Enclave Page Cache</i>
FGPA	<i>Field-programmable Gate Array</i>
FHE	<i>Fully Homomorphic Encryption</i>
FL	<i>Federated Learning</i>
GPU	<i>Graphics Processing Units</i>
HAL	<i>Hardware Abstraction Layer</i>
HE	<i>Homomorphic Encryption</i>
HSM	<i>Hardware Security Module</i>
HTTPS	<i>Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure</i>
IETF	<i>Internet Engineering Task Force</i>
IoT	<i>Internet of Things</i>
ISO	<i>International Organization for Standardization</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
ML	<i>Machine Learning</i>
MPC	<i>Multi-Party Computation</i>
NDM	<i>Nokia Data Marketplace</i>
NIST	<i>National Institute of Standards and Technology</i>
OS	<i>Operating System</i>
OTA	<i>Over-the-Air</i>

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PPC	Privacy-Preserving Computation
PSP	<i>Platform Security Processor</i>
QEMU	<i>A generic and open-source machine emulator and virtualizer</i>
RAM	<i>Random-access Memory</i>
RATS	<i>Remote ATtestation procedureS</i>
RBAC	<i>Role-based Access Control</i>
RFC	<i>Request For Comment</i>
RISC	<i>Reduced Instruction Set Computer</i>
RISC-V	<i>RISC 5th generation</i>
SAHE	<i>Software-Assisted Hardware Encryption</i>
SDK	<i>Software Development Kit</i>
SEV	<i>AMD Secure Encrypted Virtualization</i>
SGX	<i>Intel Software Guard Extensions</i>
SMA	<i>Software Management Agent</i>
SMPC	<i>Secure Multi-Party Computation</i>
STRIDE	<i>Spoofing, Tampering, Information disclosure, Denial of service, Elevation of privilege</i>
TCB	<i>Trusted Computing Base</i>
TDX	<i>Intel Trust Domain Extension</i>
TEE	<i>Trusted Execution Environment</i>
TLS	<i>Transport Layer Security</i>
TPM	<i>Trusted Platform Module</i>
UI	<i>User Interface</i>
V2I	<i>Vehicle-to-Infrastructure</i>
VM	<i>Virtual Machine</i>
VMPL	<i>Virtual Machine Privilege Level</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
ZKP	<i>Zero-knowledge Proof</i>
DLT	<i>Distributed Ledger Technology</i>

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Confidential computing is targeting to protect data in use in addition to more traditional data in transit and data at rest. CONFIDENTIAL6G project is developing enablers for confidential computing. Two main approaches envisioned are the use of Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) and the utilization of hardware-based Trusted Execution Environment (TEE). This document (D3.1) includes collection of requirements for confidential computing. There is another document (D4.1) that lists networking-related confidential networking requirements. Use case specific requirements are also collected to another document (D5.1). The requirements are used to guide the work of technical work packages of the CONFIDENTIAL6G project. In addition to the requirements, the document also contains architectural blueprints for secure and privacy-preserving computations.

Requirements are captured, organized, and managed using Volere template and divided to functional and non-functional requirements. Individual requirements are presented using IETF RFC2119 terminology describing whether the requirement is mandatory, recommended, or optional. Rationale for inclusion and fit criterion for assessment are also given. A unique identifier and one or more categories are also assigned to each requirement. Analysis of three initial use cases of CONFIDENTIAL6G project and STRIDE-based security analysis were among means of capturing requirements for confidential computing.

The architecture blueprint part of the document presents architecture design principles and identifies main software and hardware components for high-level architecture and is summarizing pros and cons of various privacy-preserving computation techniques. Technical issues of both FHE and TEE based approaches are discussed. Hardware and software component alternatives are also presented and the use of remote attestation for integrity verification is discussed. TEE approach is also discussed in more detail using AMD SEV-SNP as an example. Challenges related to TEEs and embedded platforms are also discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 OBJECTIVE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document (D3.1) is presenting requirements for CONFIDENTIAL6G work package 3 (confidential computing) with architecture blueprints. Confidential computing approaches can help to address privacy concerns. Confidential computing techniques allow data to be processed in a secure environment, even if the hardware or software is compromised. In this document, we will provide various requirements and architecture for confidential computing and privacy-preserving technologies for 6G. Confidential networking related requirements are in CONFIDENTIAL6G document D4.1. Requirements for the project use cases are available in CONFIDENTIAL6G document D5.1.

1.2 SCOPE

CONFIDENTIAL6G work package 3 is focusing on the following topics:

- **Confidential computing** is a technology that allows sensitive data to be processed securely within a hardware-isolated environment. This ensures that the data remains encrypted even while it is being processed, protecting it from unauthorized access.
- **Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)** are hardware-based security features that create isolated, secure environments within a system. They provide a trusted foundation for confidential computing.
- **Software abstractions and enablers** are software layers that simplify the interaction with TEEs. They provide a standardized way to access and utilize the capabilities of different TEE implementations, making it easier for developers to build confidential computing applications.
- **Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE)** and **Secure Multi-party Computation (SMPC)** are advanced cryptographic techniques that allow computations to be performed on encrypted data without revealing the underlying data. These techniques are particularly useful for privacy-preserving data analysis and machine learning.
- **Collaborative AI applications** refer to AI systems that involve multiple parties collaborating on data and models. Confidential computing can enable secure collaboration without compromising data privacy.

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- **IoT edge** refers to the edge devices in an IoT network, such as sensors and actuators. Confidential computing can be applied to these devices to protect sensitive data and ensure the security of IoT systems.

In essence, CONFIDENTIAL6G work package 3 aims to make confidential computing more accessible and practical by:

1. **Standardizing TEE access:** Developing software tools and mechanism to simplify the use of TEEs from different vendors.
2. **Advancing cryptographic techniques:** Researching and optimizing FHE and SMPC for real-world applications.
3. **Focusing on practical use cases:** Prioritizing the application of confidential computing to collaborative AI and IoT edge scenarios.

1.3 STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document is structured as follows. In chapter 2 privacy-preserving technologies are presented and their role in 6G technologies are discussed. Chapter 3 describes methodologies that are used to capture and organize requirements. Main functional and non-functional requirements are presented in chapter 4. Next three chapter are presenting initial requirements for CONFIDENTIAL6G use cases. Chapter 5 describes the requirements of the predictive maintenance use case. In chapter 6 requirements for the privacy-preserving computing platform for telecom cloud use case are listed. Intelligent connected vehicle use case requirements are presented in chapter 7. Next chapters are then presenting architecture topics. Chapter 8 describes architecture blueprints for confidential computing and privacy-preserving technologies. Chapter 9 covers TEE-related issues in more detail. Risks and challenges related to confidential computing are listed in chapter 10. Concluding remarks are presented in chapter 11.

2 6G AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES

2.1 6G MOBILE COMMUNICATION NETWORKS

The sixth generation (6G) of cellular networks is expected to bring a wide range of new and innovative services, many of which will require the processing of sensitive data. This raises serious privacy concerns, as malicious actors could potentially gain access to this data and use it for harmful purposes.

There has been a phenomenal advancement in mobile communication network since the first emergence of analog communications network in the 1980s. This advancement is not a one-step process, but consists of several generations which have different standards, capacities, and techniques. New generations have been introduced nearly every ten years. The evolution of the mobile network is shown in **Figure 1**, below [1].

Figure 1: Evolution of the mobile network

6G, the next frontier in cellular technology, promises to revolutionize communication with its blistering speeds, minimal lag, and ability to power cutting-edge applications like augmented reality, virtual reality, and even autonomous driving.

6G's enhanced capabilities bring both benefits and drawbacks. While its high bandwidth promises faster connections, it also raises new concerns about user privacy. The sheer volume of data that can be collected and shared opens doors to potential misuse, such as user tracking, activity monitoring, and even identification.

2.2 THREAT LANDSCAPE

The vast connectivity of 6G networks will expose new security and privacy weaknesses. Figure 2 summarizes the potential threats based on future technological, architectural, and application advancements.

Figure 2: 6G security threat landscape

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of connectivity platforms in sustaining economic and societal processes. The deployment of 5G will enhance the competitiveness and resilience of European industries by enabling digitalization and automation in various domains. However, 5G systems may not meet the performance requirements of certain applications, such as holographic communications and digital twins. Therefore, the development of 6G systems is necessary to meet these new levels of vertical performance requirements. 6G will incorporate analytic and intelligence capabilities to enable real-time decision making on high data volumes. It will also prioritize sustainability, affordability, accessibility, and security, while considering key policy challenges and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. The vision for 6G includes full-dimensional wireless coverage, combining features like sensing, connectivity, computing, and imaging to enable full-vertical applications [2].

6G applications will require a significant increase in network capacity and speed to support the projected growth in data traffic and the development of new, data-intensive technologies. These requirements are detailed in Figure 3, which highlights the need for advancements in areas such as latency, reliability, and security [3]:

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Figure 3: 6G applications, requirements, and security

2.3 SERVICE ORCHESTRATION

Service orchestration is the process of coordinating and managing the execution of multiple services to achieve a specific business goal. It involves defining the relationships between services, the flow of data between them, and the conditions under which they should be executed.

Service orchestration is a critical component of privacy-preserving computation (PPC) because it helps to ensure that sensitive data is never exposed during the computation process. PPC techniques, such as homomorphic encryption and secure multi-party computation, allow parties to collaborate on computations without revealing their private data to each other. However, these techniques can be complex to implement and manage, and service orchestration can help to streamline the process.

2.4 SECURE COLLABORATIVE AI/ML (MULTI-PARTY COMPUTATION)

Secure collaborative AI is performed by means of secure multiparty computation (SMPC), a set of cryptographic techniques that ensure that each party's private data remains confidential throughout the computation process. Secure multi-party computation (SMPC) is a cryptographic technique that enables multiple parties to jointly train and evaluate machine learning models without revealing their private

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data to each other. This technique is particularly useful in scenarios where sensitive data is involved and multiple parties need to collaborate on AI/ML tasks without compromising privacy.

SMPC protocols work by using cryptographic techniques to ensure that each party's private data remains confidential throughout the computation process. The parties exchange encrypted data and perform computations on these encrypted values without ever decrypting them. The final result of the computation is then revealed to all parties, but no individual party learns any information about the private data of the others.

SMPC protocols typically involve several steps:

1. **Input Preparation:** Each party prepares their private data in a secure format, such as homomorphic encryption.
2. **Secure Computation:** The parties jointly compute the desired machine learning model or function using secure protocols, such as secret sharing-based protocol or garbled circuits.
3. **Output Aggregation:** The parties obtain the result of the computation through aggregation without revealing their individual inputs.

2.5 OVERVIEW OF CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES

Confidential computing and privacy-preserving technologies are a set of emerging technologies that aim to protect data privacy and security in cloud computing and other computing environments. These technologies use a variety of techniques to encrypt data and applications, so that they can only be accessed by authorized users or parties. Confidential computing is a broad term that encompasses a variety of technologies, including:

- **Trusted execution environments (TEEs):** TEEs are hardware-based security solutions that provide a secure enclave within a processor or other hardware device. This enclave is isolated from the rest of the system, including the operating system and other software, and it can only be accessed by authorized code. This makes TEEs ideal for protecting sensitive data, such as encryption keys and financial information. TEEs offer protection of data in use.
- **Secure multi-party computation (SMPC):** SMPC is a cryptographic technique that allows multiple parties to compute a function on their input data without revealing their data to each other. This is done by breaking the

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computation down into a series of smaller steps, each of which is performed by a different party. The results of these steps are then combined in a way that does not reveal any of the original input data. SMPC is a powerful tool for protecting privacy in a variety of applications, such as financial fraud detection and medical research.

- **Differential privacy:** Differential privacy is a statistical technique that allows you to make accurate statistical queries about a dataset without revealing any information about individual data points. This is done by adding noise to the data in a way that preserves the overall statistical properties of the dataset but makes it impossible to identify any individual records. Differential privacy is a valuable tool for protecting privacy in a variety of applications, such as online census data collection and social media research.
- **Fully homomorphic encryption (FHE):** Fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) is a type of encryption that allows computations to be performed on encrypted data without decrypting it first. This means that sensitive data can be processed without ever being exposed to the untrusted environment, making it a powerful tool for confidential computing. FHE is used to protect data in use, which is the most vulnerable stage of the data lifecycle. When data is in use, it is decrypted and stored in memory, which makes it susceptible to attack if the underlying hardware is compromised. FHE can help to mitigate this risk by encrypting data in memory, making it inaccessible to attackers even if they gain access to the hardware. FHE is also used to protect data at rest and in transit apart from processing.
- **Zero-knowledge proof (ZKP):** A zero-knowledge proof is a cryptographic technique that allows one party (the prover) to prove to another party (the verifier) that they possess certain information or have performed a specific computation without revealing the information or the computation itself. This is crucial for preserving privacy and security in confidential computing scenarios where sensitive data is processed in an untrusted environment.
- **Hardware security modules (HSMs):** These are specialized devices that provide cryptographic functions and secure storage for sensitive data.
- **Software-based security solutions:** These solutions use encryption and other techniques to protect data and applications in software.
- **Privacy-preserving technologies** are a subset of confidential computing technologies that focus on protecting the privacy of sensitive data while it is being processed. These technologies use techniques such as differential privacy and homomorphic encryption to ensure that the results of computations cannot be used to identify individual data points.

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Figure 4 shows how the technologies we consider apply to the privacy goals outlined above. The goal of Input Privacy is primarily addressed by secure computation technologies, techniques that compute on data while it remains encrypted or otherwise obfuscated from regular access and Zero Knowledge proofs of knowledge that prove claims without revealing the input data on which those claims are based. Sometimes these technologies also provide the means to enforce access control policy on a flexible basis.

Figure 4: Venn diagram showing which privacy goals are fulfilled by which privacy techniques.

The goal of output privacy is primarily addressed by technologies such as differential privacy techniques that prevent those with access to computed results from “reverse engineering” those computations to learn about input data.

The goal of policy enforcement is primarily addressed by access control policies and enforcement points for those policies, for example by allowing only certain queries over data to be answered by a system [4].

However, there are also some challenges associated with using confidential computing and privacy-preserving technologies:

- **Complexity:** These technologies can be complex to implement and manage.
- **Performance overhead:** These technologies can introduce some performance overhead, which may be a concern for some applications.

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- **Lack of standards:** There is currently no single standard for confidential computing, which can make it difficult to interoperate between different systems.

3 FRAMEWORK AND STANDARD FOR CAPTURING REQUIREMENTS

3.1 VOLERE TEMPLATE

The Volere template is a comprehensive framework for capturing, organizing, and managing requirements during the software development process. It is designed to ensure that requirements are clear, concise, testable, and traceable [5].

Table 1 provides a comprehensive list of fields which are used within the Volere template.

Table 1: Volere template – attribute description

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
ID	Each requirement is uniquely identified
Description	The description is the intent of the requirement. It is a statement about what the system has to fulfil according to the rationale (see further below).
Categories	<p>Technical or non-technical topics covered by the requirement. Could be more than one.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Privacy • Security • Trust • Performance • Scalability • Platform • Networking • Edge computing • Cloud computing • Machine learning • Latency • Interoperability • Management • Data • Discovery • Look-up • Load balancing • Bandwidth

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6G
Rationale	The rationale is the reason behind the requirement’s existence. It explains why the requirement is important and how it contributes to the system’s purpose.
Fit Criterion	A quantification or measurement to assess to which extent the original requirement has been eventually implemented or taken into account within the system. Can be used as the “Definition-of-Done” in agile development practices.

3.2 INDICATING REQUIREMENT LEVELS

IETF RFC 2119 [6] is a technical document published by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) that provides a set of keywords and their definitions to be used in technical specifications. These keywords are intended to clarify the level of compliance or obligation associated with specific requirements or recommendations.

The keywords and their meanings:

The RFC defines the following keywords and their corresponding meanings:

1. **MUST:** This indicates a mandatory requirement. A specification **MUST** be strictly followed to be considered compliant.
2. **MUST NOT:** This indicates a prohibition. A specification **MUST NOT** be followed to be considered compliant.
3. **REQUIRED:** This is synonymous with "MUST".
4. **SHALL:** This is synonymous with “MUST”.
5. **SHALL NOT:** This is synonymous with “MUST NOT”.
6. **SHOULD:** This indicates a strong recommendation. It is expected that most implementations will follow this, but it is not strictly required.
7. **SHOULD NOT:** This indicates a strong recommendation against doing something. It is expected that most implementations will not follow this, but it is not strictly prohibited.
8. **MAY:** This indicates permission. An implementation may or may not follow this.
9. **OPTIONAL:** This is synonymous with "MAY."

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10. Example Usage

Consider the following example:

- "A compliant server **MUST** implement the TLS protocol." This clearly states that TLS is mandatory for compliance.
- "A server **SHOULD** support the HTTP/2 protocol." This suggests that HTTP/2 is recommended but not strictly required.

3.3 USE OF IETF RFC STANDARDS IN VOLERE TEMPLATE

IETF RFC 2119 standard can be used in the Volere template. RFC 2119 provides a set of key words (like "MUST", "SHOULD", "MAY") to indicate requirement levels in technical specifications¹. These keywords can be very useful in clearly defining requirements within the Volere template, which is designed for capturing and managing requirements in a structured way.

Incorporating RFC 2119 terminology, ensures that the requirements are unambiguous and standardized, which can help in maintaining clarity and consistency throughout the project documentation.

The table to be used for the requirements is as shown below.

Table 2: Requirement template format

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion

4 PRIVACY-PRESERVING COMPUTATION (PPC) SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

4.1 THREAT ANALYSIS

Threat modelling is a systematic process of identifying, analyzing, and prioritizing potential threats to a system or application. By proactively identifying and addressing these threats, organizations can significantly reduce the risk of security breaches and data loss.

Threat Analysis involves breaking down a system into components and analyzing each component for potential threats and vulnerabilities.

The STRIDE [7](Spoofing identity, tampering with data, Repudiation threats, Information disclosure, (Distributed) Denial of service and Elevation of privileges) model is a useful tool for threats classification.

A STRIDE analysis can be used in the early phase. STRIDE is based on a reference architecture for determining the overall image of a system. The purpose of threat modelling is to understand how an attacker could penetrate the system.

The following table gives some examples of threats, their definition, potential scenarios and the countermeasure that could be undertaken in order to face the threat.

Table 3: STRIDE description

Threat	Property Violated	Definition	Expected scenarios	Measures
Spoofing	Authentication	Impersonalizing something or someone else.	If the system user settings are not set properly, attackers might spoof them	Set the password appropriately: SSH Login with private key
Tampering	Integrity	Modifying data or code	If an illegal program has access to a cryptographic key or an encryption mechanism that holds the cryptographic key, the software replaced will misuse the real ID of device	MAC Applying a tamper-proof mechanism to the device

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Repudiation	Accountability	Claiming to have not performed an action.	If the user does not have a log of the communication, it is likely to negate the fact of the operation that the user performed improperly	Acquisition and maintenance of various logs
Information disclosure	Confidentiality	Exposing information to someone not authorized to see it	The attacker exploits the encrypted key and obtains the encryption key and decryption key between nodes	Implemented Anti-malware, Secure Key Management
Denial of service	Availability	Deny or degrade Service to users	The function might be stopped if unauthorized access is performed over a network	Apply response limit
Elevation of privileges	Authorization	Gain capabilities without proper authorization	Allowing a user to run commands as admin	Restrict users who can get administrator rights

In the following there is an analysis of the threats for different components of confidential privacy preserving computing based on the STRIDE framework:

Table 4: STRIDE for Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)

Threat	Description	Mitigation
Spoofing	Spoofing in the context of TEEs involves an attacker impersonating the TEE environment to trick applications into running in an untrusted environment.	Use hardware-based attestation to verify the authenticity of the TEE. Example: Imagine a banking application that runs sensitive operations within a TEE. An attacker could try to spoof the TEE, making the application believe it is running in a secure environment when it is not. Hardware-based attestation ensures that the application can verify the TEE's authenticity before executing sensitive operations.

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<p>Tampering</p>	<p>Tampering involves modifying data or code within the TEE.</p>	<p>Ensure data and code integrity through cryptographic checks and secure boot processes.</p> <p>Example: An attacker might try to alter the code of a financial application running in a TEE to manipulate transactions. Cryptographic checks and secure boot processes ensure that any tampering is detected, and the system can prevent the altered code from running.</p>
<p>Repudiation</p>	<p>Repudiation involves users denying actions performed within the TEE.</p>	<p>Implement logging and auditing mechanisms within the TEE to provide non-repudiable evidence.</p> <p>Example: If a user denies initiating a transaction processed within a TEE, detailed logs and audit trails can provide evidence of the action, ensuring accountability.</p>
<p>Information Disclosure</p>	<p>Sensitive data processed within the TEE could be exposed.</p>	<p>encrypt data within the TEE and use secure channels for data transmission.</p> <p>Example: If sensitive user data is processed within a TEE, encryption ensures that even if an attacker gains access to the data, it remains unreadable without the decryption keys.</p>
<p>Denial of Service (DoS)</p>	<p>Attackers could flood the TEE with requests to exhaust resources.</p>	<p>Implement rate limiting and resource management policies.</p> <p>Example: An attacker might send a large number of requests to a TEE, trying to overwhelm it and disrupt its operations. Rate limiting ensures that the TEE can handle requests efficiently without being overwhelmed.</p>

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Elevation of Privilege	Attackers might exploit vulnerabilities to gain higher privileges within the TEE.	<p>Regularly update and patch the TEE firmware and software.</p> <p>Example: If an attacker finds a vulnerability in the TEE software, they could exploit it to gain unauthorized access. Regular updates and patches help fix these vulnerabilities, preventing such attacks.</p>
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Table 5: STRIDE for Homomorphic Encryption (HE)

Threat	Description	Mitigation
Spoofing	Attackers might spoof the encryption keys to decrypt sensitive data.	<p>Use strong key management practices and multi-factor authentication.</p> <p>Example: An attacker could try to use a fake encryption key to decrypt sensitive data. Strong key management and multi-factor authentication ensure that only authorized users can access the correct encryption keys.</p>
Tampering	Modifying encrypted data to produce incorrect results	<p>Use cryptographic integrity checks to detect tampering.</p> <p>Example: If an attacker alters encrypted data, cryptographic integrity checks can detect the changes, ensuring that the data remains accurate and untampered.</p>
Repudiation	Denying the generation or use of encryption keys.	<p>Maintain detailed logs of key generation and usage.</p> <p>Example: If a user denies generating or using an encryption key, detailed logs can provide evidence of the key's creation and usage, ensuring accountability.</p>

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Information Disclosure	Encrypted data might be exposed if keys are compromised.	Use secure key storage solutions and rotate keys regularly. Example: If an encryption key is compromised, the encrypted data could be exposed. Secure key storage and regular key rotation ensure that even if a key is compromised, the data remains protected.
Denial of Service (DoS)	Overloading the system with encryption/decryption requests.	Implement rate limiting and load balancing. Example: An attacker might send a large number of encryption/decryption requests to overwhelm the system. Rate limiting and load balancing ensure that the system can handle requests efficiently without being overwhelmed.
Elevation of Privilege	Gaining unauthorized access to encryption keys.	Enforce strict access controls and regular audits. Example: If an attacker gains unauthorized access to encryption keys, they could decrypt sensitive data. Strict access controls and regular audits ensure that only authorized users can access the keys.

Table 6: STRIDE for Secure Multiparty Computation (SMPC)

Threat	Description	Mitigation
Spoofing	Impersonating a party in the computation.	Use strong authentication mechanisms for all parties. Example: In a collaborative computation involving multiple parties, an attacker could impersonate one of the parties to manipulate the results. Strong authentication ensures that only legitimate parties can participate.

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Tampering	Altering the data or computation process.	<p>Use cryptographic protocols to ensure data integrity and correctness.</p> <p>Example: If an attacker alters the data or computation process, cryptographic protocols can detect and prevent such tampering, ensuring accurate results.</p>
Repudiation	Denying participation in the computation.	<p>Implement non-repudiable logging of all computation steps.</p> <p>Example: If a party denies participating in the computation, non-repudiable logs can provide evidence of their involvement, ensuring accountability.</p>
Information Disclosure	Leaking intermediate computation results.	<p>Use secure multi-party computation protocols that do not reveal intermediate states.</p> <p>Example: If intermediate results are leaked during computation, it could compromise the privacy of the data. Secure protocols ensure that only the final result is revealed, protecting intermediate states.</p>
Denial of Service (DoS)	Disrupting the computation process.	<p>Implement fault-tolerant protocols and redundancy.</p> <p>Example: An attacker might try to disrupt the computation process by causing failures. Fault-tolerant protocols and redundancy ensure that the computation can continue despite disruptions.</p>
Elevation of Privilege	Gaining unauthorized control over the computation process.	<p>Enforce strict role-based access controls.</p> <p>Example: If an attacker gains unauthorized control over the computation process, they could manipulate the results. Role-based access controls ensure that only authorized users can control the computation.</p>

Table 7: STRIDE for Blockchain

Threat	Description	Mitigation
Spoofing	Creating fake identities to manipulate the blockchain.	<p>Use decentralized identity verification mechanisms.</p> <p>Example: An attacker could create fake identities to manipulate transactions on the blockchain. Decentralized identity verification ensures that only legitimate identities can participate.</p>
Tampering	Altering blockchain data.	<p>Use cryptographic hashing and consensus mechanisms to ensure data integrity.</p> <p>Example: If an attacker tries to alter blockchain data, cryptographic hashing and consensus mechanisms can detect and prevent such tampering, ensuring data integrity.</p>
Repudiation	Denying transactions or actions on the blockchain.	<p>Implement immutable logging and cryptographic signatures.</p> <p>Example: If a user denies a transaction on the blockchain, immutable logs and cryptographic signatures can provide evidence of the transaction, ensuring accountability.</p>
Information Disclosure	Exposing sensitive transaction data.	<p>Use privacy-preserving techniques like zero-knowledge proofs.</p> <p>Example: If sensitive transaction data is exposed, it could compromise privacy. Privacy-preserving techniques like zero-knowledge proofs ensure that transaction details remain confidential.</p>
Denial of Service (DoS)	Overloading the blockchain network.	<p>Implement rate limiting and scalable consensus algorithms.</p> <p>Example: An attacker might try to overload the blockchain network with transactions. Rate limiting and scalable consensus algorithms ensure that the network can</p>

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		handle transactions efficiently without being overwhelmed.
Elevation of Privilege	Gaining unauthorized control over the blockchain network.	Use decentralized governance and strict access controls. Example: If an attacker gains unauthorized control over the blockchain network, they could manipulate transactions. Decentralized governance and strict access controls ensure that only authorized users can control the network.

4.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 8: Functional requirements – privacy-preserving computation

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_F_1	Access Control	The system SHALL enable role-based access control (RBAC) to restrict data access based on user roles and permissions.	To limit data access to authorized users only.	RBAC policies are defined and enforced through a centralized access management system.
WP3_F_2	Data Privacy	The system MUST ensure data encryption at rest and in transit using state-of-the-art cryptographic techniques.	To protect sensitive data from unauthorized access.	Data encryption verified through security audits and compliance checks.
WP3_F_3	Data Privacy	The system MUST ensure that all data processed within TEEs is encrypted	To protect sensitive data from unauthorized access and breaches.	Data is encrypted using AES-256 or higher encryption standards.
WP3_F_4	Data Integrity	The system MUST ensure data integrity and confidentiality.	To protect data from tampering and	Uses blockchain for data integrity.

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			unauthorized access.	
WP3_F_5	Data Processing	The system MUST support secure multi-party computation (MPC) to enable collaborative data processing without exposing raw data.	To allow multiple parties to compute on data without revealing it to each other.	MPC protocols are implemented and verified through formal security proofs.
WP3_F_6	Data Anonymization	The system SHALL implement differential privacy techniques to ensure that individual data points cannot be re-identified.	To protect individual privacy while allowing data analysis.	Differential privacy mechanisms are applied with a configurable privacy budget.
WP3_F_7	Data Sharing	The system SHALL support secure data sharing using blockchain-based smart contracts.	To facilitate secure and controlled data exchange between parties.	Smart contracts are deployed on the blockchain to manage data sharing agreements.
WP3_F_8	Data Verification	The system SHALL implement zero-knowledge proofs (ZKPs) to verify data integrity without revealing the data itself.	To ensure data integrity while maintaining confidentiality.	ZKPs are used to prove data properties without disclosing the data.
WP3_F_9	Auditability	The system SHALL use blockchain to maintain an immutable audit trail of all data access and processing activities.	To provide transparency and accountability for data handling.	All transactions are recorded on a blockchain ledger with tamper-proof properties.
WP3_F_10	Trust	The system MUST provide mechanisms for secure key management.	To ensure that encryption keys are securely stored and managed.	Keys are stored in a hardware security module (HSM).
WP3_F_11	Networking	The system MUST support secure networking protocols.	To protect data during transmission.	Uses TLS 1.3 for all communications.

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WP3_F_12	Edge Computing	The system SHOULD support edge computing capabilities.	To enable processing at the edge of the network.	Edge nodes process data locally.
WP3_F_13	Cloud Computing	The system MUST integrate with cloud computing platforms.	To leverage cloud resources for scalability and flexibility.	System integrates with AWS, Azure, and Google Cloud.
WP3_F_14	Machine Learning	The system SHOULD support machine learning workloads.	To enable privacy-preserving machine learning.	Supports TensorFlow and PyTorch.
WP3_F_15		To enable privacy-preserving collaborative AI/ML,		Uses homomorphic encryption and secure multi-party computation protocols.
WP3_F_16	Integrity Verification	The system MUST provide remote attestation capabilities to verify the integrity of TEEs before processing data.	To ensure that data is processed in a trusted environment.	Remote attestation is performed using industry-standard protocols like Intel SGX or ARM TrustZone.
WP3_F_17	TEE	<p>The system SHOULD provide a consistent, vendor-agnostic API for common TEE operations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secure data storage and retrieval • Secure key generation and management • Remote attestation • Secure execution of code • Secure communication 	A single, consistent API simplifies the development process, reducing the learning curve and minimizing the risk of errors.	The API should cover all essential TEE operations, including secure data storage, key management, remote attestation, secure execution, and secure communication

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WP3_F_18	TEE	The system SHOULD automatically detect and configure available TEEs.	TEEs provide a secure environment for sensitive operations, protecting critical data and code from potential threats. By automatically detecting and configuring available TEEs, the system can proactively leverage this security feature without manual intervention.	Automatically identify available TEEs during the system startup process.
WP3_F_19	TEE	The system SHOULD provide users a mechanism to choose the desired TEE or let the System select the most suitable one based on specific criteria (e.g., security level, performance)	<p>Allowing users to choose their preferred TEE provides them with granular control over their data's security and performance requirements. This empowers users to make informed decisions based on their specific needs.</p> <p>Automating TEE selection based on predefined criteria ensures</p>	<p>System must support a diverse range of TEEs to accommodate various user preferences and system constraints.</p> <p>System should be compatible with popular TEE platforms like Intel SGX, ARM TrustZone, and others.</p>

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			optimal performance and security for users who may not have the expertise to make informed choices.	
WP3_F_20	TEE	The system MUST provide mechanism to verify the authenticity and integrity of TEE environments.	TEE environments are designed to securely execute sensitive computations. Verifying their authenticity and integrity ensures that the environment is genuine, has not been tampered with, and is running as intended.	<p>Ensure that only trusted and verified bootloaders and operating systems are loaded into the TEE environment.</p> <p>Utilize cryptographic signatures to verify the integrity of each boot component.</p> <p>Allow remote entities to verify the authenticity and integrity of the TEE environment.</p>
WP3_F_21	TEE	The system SHOULD allow users to create and manage secure enclaves within TEEs.	Enclaves provide a secure, isolated execution environment within a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE). This isolation significantly reduces the attack surface, making it harder for malicious	<p>Provide a user-friendly interface to create new enclaves.</p> <p>Allow users to define the enclave's security policies, including access controls and data protection mechanisms.</p> <p>Enable efficient management of</p>

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			<p>actors to compromise sensitive data and operations.</p> <p>By executing sensitive computations within enclaves, organizations can protect confidential information from unauthorized access, even if the host system is compromised.</p>	<p>multiple enclaves, including provisioning, configuration, and deletion.</p>
WP3_F_22	TEE	The system MUST enable the secure destruction of enclaves when no longer needed.	Enclaves, being isolated execution environments, can potentially hold sensitive data. Once their purpose is served, their continued existence could pose a security risk if not properly destroyed.	Ensure the complete removal of all enclave-related data, including code, configuration, and any residual data.
WP3_F_23	TEE	The system MUST Ensure the secure deletion of sensitive data from the TEE.	Sensitive data, such as personal information, financial records, or intellectual property, must be protected from unauthorized	The secure deletion process should be regularly tested and validated to ensure its effectiveness.

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			<p>access, disclosure, or misuse.</p> <p>Secure deletion ensures that this data cannot be recovered.</p>	
WP3_F_24	TEE	The system SHOULD provide mechanism to manage cryptographic keys within the TEE, ensuring secure storage and usage.	<p>By storing and managing cryptographic keys within a Trusted Execution Environment (TEE), we significantly enhance the security posture of the system.</p> <p>TEEs are isolated hardware-based environments that protect sensitive data and code from unauthorized access, even if the host system is compromised.</p>	<p>Keys must be stored in a tamper-resistant and physically isolated memory region within the TEE.</p> <p>Access to keys should be restricted to authorized software components running within the TEE.</p> <p>Strong encryption algorithms should be used to protect keys while they are stored and transmitted.</p>
WP3_F_25	Model Sharing	The system MUST provide mechanisms for secure model sharing.	To enable collaborative model development while protecting intellectual property.	Secure model sharing mechanisms are in place and functioning correctly.

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WP3_F_26	Homomorphic Encryption	The system MUST support homomorphic encryption for computations.	To perform computations on encrypted data without decrypting it.	Homomorphic encryption is implemented and operational.
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4.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 9: Non-functional requirements – privacy-preserving computation

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_NF_1	Regulatory Compliance	The system MUST ensure compliance with relevant data protection regulations (e.g., GDPR, CCPA).	To adhere to legal requirements for data privacy.	Compliance is verified through regular audits and assessments.
WP3_NF_2	Regulatory Compliance	The system MUST provide mechanisms for data subjects to exercise their rights (e.g., access, rectification, deletion).	To comply with data protection laws and respect user privacy.	User requests are handled through a secure and transparent process.
WP3_NF_3	Robustness	The blockchain protocol MUST be robust and resistant to known attack vectors.	To ensure the security and reliability of the blockchain.	Blockchain protocol is resistant to Sybil attacks, double-spending attacks, and 51% attacks.
WP3_NF_4	Reliability	Smart contracts MUST be carefully designed, reviewed, and tested.	To prevent vulnerabilities and unintended behaviour.	Smart contracts are secure and function as intended.
WP3_NF_5	Security	Blockchain keys MUST be managed securely.	To prevent unauthorized access and compromise.	Strong key generation, storage methods, and secure key rotation procedures are in place.
WP3_NF_6	Performance	The system MUST minimize latency for real-time applications.	To ensure timely processing of data.	Latency is less than a defined time.

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WP3_NF_7	Scalability	The system SHALL scale horizontally to accommodate increased load.	To support growing user base and data volume.	System can add nodes dynamically.
WP3_NF_8	Performance	The system MUST minimize latency for real-time applications.	To ensure timely processing of data.	Latency is less than 10ms.
WP3_NF_9	Performance	The system SHOULD support a large number of concurrent users and devices	Ensures the system can handle increased network traffic.	The system should maintain performance increased concurrent users.
WP3_NF_10	Load Balancing	The system SHALL ensure fair load balancing across nodes.	To optimize resource utilization.	Load balancer distributes traffic evenly.
WP3_NF_11	Usability	The system SHOULD provide user-friendly documentation and support resources.	Facilitates ease of use and adoption by developers and operators.	Documentation should include API references, integration guides, and troubleshooting tips
WP3_NF_12	Availability	The system MUST have high availability and reliability.	To ensure continuous operation and minimize downtime.	System uptime is maintained at 99.9% or higher.
WP3_NF_13	Interoperability	The system SHALL be platform-agnostic.	To ensure compatibility across different hardware and software environments.	Runs on Windows, Linux, and macOS.
WP3_NF_14	Interoperability	The system MUST be platform-agnostic to support multiple hardware vendors.	To ensure interoperability across different hardware platforms.	System supports Intel SGX, AMD SEV, and ARM TrustZone.

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WP3_NF_15	Interoperability	The system MUST support interoperability with existing AI/ML tools and platforms.	To enable seamless integration and collaboration.	Interoperability with major AI/ML tools and platforms is demonstrated.
WP3_NF_16	Maintenance	The system MUST support regular updates and maintenance.	To keep the system up-to-date with the latest security patches and features.	Regular updates and maintenance schedules are adhered to.
WP3_NF_17	Energy Efficiency	To ensure sustainable and cost-effective privacy-preserving computations.	The system must demonstrate a reduction in energy consumption.	<p>TEEs: Optimize energy usage by leveraging hardware acceleration and minimizing idle power consumption.</p> <p>Homomorphic Encryption: Use efficient algorithms that reduce computational overhead, such as batching operations and using approximate HE schemes.</p> <p>SMPC: Minimize communication rounds and computational complexity.</p>
WP3_NF_17	Energy Efficiency	To ensure energy-saving measures do not compromise reliability and correctness.	The system must pass all reliability tests with energy-saving features enabled.	TEEs: Ensure energy-saving features do not interfere with integrity checks and secure execution guarantees.

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				<p>Homomorphic Encryption: Maintain accuracy of computations on encrypted data, with energy-saving measures not introducing significant errors.</p> <p>SMPC: Ensure protocols maintain correctness and security guarantees.</p>
	User interface	System SHOULD provide a user-friendly interface for managing TEEs and developing applications.	<p>A user-friendly interface is crucial for a system that involves complex tasks like managing Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) and developing applications.</p> <p>Such an interface can significantly reduce the learning curve for both technical and non-technical users, leading to increased efficiency and productivity.</p>	The interface should follow established design principles, such as clear labelling, consistent layout, and intuitive navigation.

5 USE CASE 1: PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FOR AIRLINE CONSORTIUM

5.1 USE CASE OBJECTIVES AND RELATION TO PROJECT OBJECTIVES

This use-case implements a platform for secure and trackable data sharing between aviation companies, manufacturers, regulation bodies and other organizations. The main goal is to enable predictive maintenance, driven by AI/ML, on top of shared data. Aviation companies dispose huge amounts of valuable data however algorithms trained on data sets collected by a single company are not precise enough due to the fact that each individual company has a limited number of certain types of aeroplane in their fleet. Hence, data is very valuable, but companies with competing interests are not willing to share their data easily. The aim of this use case is to showcase how privacy-preserving computation and secure data sharing via blockchain could help to overcome the aforementioned challenges. Technologies that will be utilised include blockchain networks with confidential Smart Contracts and Fully Homomorphic Encryption to enable private transactions that log data exchange. Further, federated AI/ML will be applied in order for confidential containers carrying algorithms to be transported over Kubernetes clusters to the edge data centres that are placed near the airports. This is done not only because data is private and it should not leave the premise, but also because in this particular case data is huge, and time for algorithm application is often very short (between two flights), so in many cases it is even not possible to move data centrally. Finally - FHE and SMPC will be applied to ensure that data set from each organisation stays encrypted while the algorithm is applied.

Key KPIs include the increase in trustworthiness of container orchestration for multi-party computation and increase in efficiency with federated AI/ML for large consortiums and large data sets.

5.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 10: UC1 functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC1_F_1	Data Privacy	The system MUST ensure that sensitive data remains confidential during	Data confidentiality is maintained throughout the analysis and model training processes.	To protect sensitive information from unauthorized access.

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		analysis and model training.		
WP3_UC1_F_2	Data Privacy	The system MUST protect the privacy of trained predictive maintenance models.	Models are protected from reverse engineering attempts.	Models are protected from reverse engineering attempts.
WP3_UC1_F_3	Data Provenance	The system MUST ensure the provenance of airline data is traceable.	Data provenance is traceable and verifiable.	To ensure accountability and prevent data manipulation.
WP3_UC1_F_4	Storage	The system MUST store airline data in secure environments.	Data is stored in dedicated repositories or encrypted blockchain nodes.	To protect data from unauthorized access and breaches.
WP3_UC1_F_5	Audit Log	The software used in the system MUST generate audit logs for data and model access.	Audit logs are generated and maintained.	To track access and ensure accountability.
WP3_UC1_F_6	Analysis and learning	The system MUST be able to infer from the data the status of an aircraft engine and whether there are any issues (faults) that necessitate maintenance actions.	Predictive maintenance capabilities to identify potential aircraft engine faults early and enable proactive maintenance actions.	The mechanisms for predicting aircraft engine faults have an accuracy of at least 85%.
WP3_UC1_F_7	Analysis and learning	The system SHOULD be able to derive insights from encrypted data.		
WP3_UC1_F_8	Data Management	The system MUST enable utilization of aircraft maintenance data from diverse data sources (e.g. IoT devices, maintenance systems of different business entities), without sharing raw data.		

5.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 11: UC1 non-functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC1_NF_1	Interoperability	The system SHOULD be compatible with existing airline maintenance systems.	To ensure seamless integration and data exchange with current systems.	Compatibility MUST be verified through integration testing with different airline maintenance systems.

6 USE CASE 2: PRIVACY-PRESERVING CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING PLATFORM

6.1 USE CASE OBJECTIVES AND RELATION TO PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The use case UC2 describes enablement of confidential computing to support telecom clouds aiming to demonstrate simplification of configuration and deployment of confidential computing and improving quantum safety. This will be done by utilizing the results of CONFIDENTIAL6G technical work packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4).

The use case will demonstrate automated handling of confidential VMs, including their creation and initialization in a programmable manner and using cloud APIs. The mechanism includes TEE abstractions and software framework for handling remote attestations. The use case description also includes technology and architecture design decisions by mentioning confidential containers with Kubernetes support and the use of software management agent component to manage confidential virtual machines and TLS connections.

The use case description lists seven KPIs:

- 50% simplification for deploying confidential VMs.
- 30% finer-grained remote attestation handling configuration.
- Enablement of quantum-safe TLS support within secure enclaves.
- Enablement of Kubernetes support for confidential containers.
- Execution time of algorithm inside TEE cannot be slower than 15% to 20% compared to a non-TEE execution time.
- Reduce attested TLS latency.
- Orchestrate at least 5 parallel computation executions on single machine.

6.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In addition to generic requirements specified earlier, the following use case specific functional requirements were identified from the use case description.

Table 12: UC2 functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC2_F_1	Cloud computing	Cloud orchestration SHOULD provide	Hide complexity from end-users and provide	Support for at least two platforms, e.g.,

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		automatic enablement of virtual machines.	vendor-neutral way to use TEEs.	AMD SEV and Intel TDX.
WP3_UC2_F_2	Cloud computing	Cloud orchestration SHOULD be able to orchestrate also confidential containers.	Users would like to use widely used familiar tools.	Support added to one widely used tool, e.g., Kubernetes.
WP3_UC2_F_3	Cloud computing	Dedicated set of nodes MAY be reserved for confidential orchestration.	Isolate confidential computing from the rest of the system.	Verify that the nodes in the dedicated set are not used elsewhere.
WP3_UC2_F_4	Platform	Management component SHOULD handle remote attestation	Centralize management to one component to ease maintenance.	Verify architecture design.

6.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In addition to generic requirements specified earlier, the following use case specific non-functional requirements were identified from the initial use case description.

Table 13. UC2 non-functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC2_NF_1	Platform, Maintainability	Confidential Toolkit MAY be used to develop confidential computing solutions.	Ease development and maintenance of confidential computing solutions.	Toolkit in use.
WP3_UC2_NF_2	Platform, Interoperability	Platform independent confidential computing hardware platform abstractions SHOULD be provided.	The platform abstraction should hide non-relevant platform dependent features.	There should be support for multiple architectures.
WP3_UC2_NF_3	Platform, Interoperability	Interoperable remote attestation MUST be used to verify integrity	Use standardized interoperable	Support for multiple architectures.

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		and authenticity of remote platforms.	mechanisms and formats.	
WP3_UC2_NF_5	Platform, Maintainability	Management component SHOULD handle management of secure VMs.	Centralize management to one component to ease maintenance.	Verify architecture design.

7 USE CASE 3: INTELLIGENT CONNECTED VEHICLE

7.1 USE CASE OBJECTIVES AND RELATION TO PROJECT OBJECTIVES

The relevance of **confidential computing** in this use case lies in ensuring the **secure processing and sharing** of sensitive data generated during Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications and over-the-air (OTA) vehicle updates. As the use case integrates data from multiple sources, including in-vehicle modules and roadside infrastructure, **confidential computing** provides a mechanism to protect this data during AI/ML model training and decentralized learning, safeguarding it from exposure or tampering in untrusted environments. This will be done by utilizing the results of CONFIDENTIAL6G technical work packages (WP2, WP3, and WP4).

There are four KPIs that could be relevant to your use case, focusing on secure Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications, decentralized learning, and confidential computing:

- AI/ML model accuracy in predicting driving behaviours or road conditions should be >85%.
- 25% increase in the frequency of federated learning model updates due to decentralized training and confidential data sharing mechanisms.
- 100% encrypted and secure data transmission between vehicles and infrastructure, verified using remote attestation and TEE-based data sharing.
- 20% reduction in the time required to deploy confidential VMs and containers for secure decentralized learning.

7.2 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In addition to generic requirements specified earlier, the following use case specific functional requirements were identified from the use case description.

Table 14: UC3 functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC3_F_1	Federated Learning	The distributed learning framework SHOULD securely train models using decentralized data	Ensure data privacy during training by keeping data local (on-device) and only sharing model updates.	Ensure that confidential computing capabilities are used to protect the data during

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				model training and transmission.
WP3_UC3_F_2	Confidential Data Sharing	Confidential computing platforms SHOULD support secure and encrypted data sharing between vehicles and infrastructure.	Support secure over-the-air (OTA) updates for vehicle systems, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality.	Ensure that the data is only accessible to authorized participants through proper attestation mechanisms.
WP3_UC3_F_3	Remote Attestation	The platform SHOULD handle remote attestation to verify the integrity of devices participating in federated learning.	The platform SHOULD handle remote attestation to verify the integrity of devices participating in federated learning.	Automate remote attestation processes to ensure scalability and efficiency across the V2I network.
WP3_UC3_F_4	Cloud Orchestration for Federated Learning	Cloud orchestration SHOULD support automatic provisioning and management of confidential VMs for federated learning tasks.	Allow for the integration of popular tools to manage confidential computing workloads	Ensure that federated learning workflows can be run on secure, isolated cloud environments.

7.3 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

In addition to generic requirements specified earlier, the following use case specific non-functional requirements were identified from the use case description

Table 15: UC3 non-functional requirements

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP3_UC3_NF_1	Security, Reliability	Confidential computing infrastructure MUST ensure high availability and data integrity even in the	Mission-critical V2I communications and decentralized learning require	System uptime should be high and data recovery mechanisms should prevent

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		event of hardware failure or network disruptions.	high system reliability and security to ensure uninterrupted operation.	any data loss during confidential computing tasks.
WP3_UC3_NF_2	Performance, Scalability	The distributed learning framework SHOULD scale efficiently to accommodate a large number of connected vehicles and roadside infrastructure units.	Scalability is critical to handle increasing numbers of vehicles, data inputs, and AI model updates in real-time.	The system should support large number of vehicles and infrastructure units without performance degradation, maintaining latency below 100ms for V2I communication.
WP3_UC3_NF_3	Interoperability, Security	Confidential computing solutions SHOULD be compatible with cryptographic standards for secure data sharing and model training.	Interoperability across different hardware and software platforms is necessary for broader adoption in diverse automotive and infrastructure environments.	Support one TEE platform and adherence to cryptographic
WP3_UC3_NF_5	Maintainability, Flexibility	The confidential computing framework SHOULD be easily extensible to integrate future AI/ML models and support emerging vehicular technologies.	As new AI models and technologies evolve, the system must adapt without extensive reconfiguration or redeployment.	The system should allow integration of new AI/ML modules and be adaptable to new V2I protocols within six months without major architectural changes.

8 ARCHITECTURE BLUEPRINTS

8.1 HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

Distributed computations have become increasingly prevalent in modern data processing, offering scalability, fault tolerance, and enhanced performance. However, ensuring the security and privacy of distributed computations is a critical challenge, especially when dealing with sensitive data.

Below various software and hardware components are listed that can be used to guarantee the secure and privacy-preserving characteristics of distributed computations.

Software Components:

- Secure Multiparty Computation (SMPC)
- Differential Privacy
- Federated Learning
- Zero Knowledge Proofs
- Fully Homomorphic Encryption

Hardware Components:

- Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs)
- Secure Enclaves
- Hardware Security Modules (HSMs)

The choice of PPC technique will depend on the specific application and the desired level of privacy. In some cases, it may be necessary to use a combination of techniques to achieve the desired level of security. Table 16 summarizes the pros and cons of each PPC technique:

Table 16: Privacy-preserving technologies pros and cons

Technique	Pros	Cons
Federated Learning	<p>Privacy-preserving training: Trains models on distributed data without sharing it.</p> <p>Local data utilization: Leverages local data, reducing reliance on centralized servers.</p>	<p>Communication overhead: Requires frequent data exchange between devices, increasing bandwidth usage.</p> <p>Accuracy challenges: Can lead to lower model accuracy compared to centralized training.</p>

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SMPC	<p>Enables joint analysis of data without revealing individual data points - Offers strong privacy guarantees - Suitable for collaborative data analysis, fraud detection, etc.</p>	<p>Computationally expensive, limited scalability. - Complex setup and requires trust in the computing platform.</p>
TEE	<p>Data stays encrypted within the TEE, never leaving the secure enclave. This protects against unauthorized access and manipulation.</p> <p>TEE leverages dedicated hardware features to ensure isolation and tamper-resistance, making it robust against software attacks.</p> <p>Modern TEE solutions can handle large datasets and complex computations efficiently.</p> <p>TEEs can be used for various privacy-preserving applications, including secure data processing, machine learning, and cryptographic operations.</p> <p>TEEs are increasingly integrated with cloud platforms, enabling secure computation on remote servers.</p>	<p>Current commercial TEE solutions like SGX and TrustZone have encountered numerous vulnerabilities, raising concerns about trusting both the hardware vendor and the cloud provider. In some cases, these vulnerabilities have even been exploited to compromise the entire system, including other TEEs running on the same machine. While promising initiatives like RISC-V based TEEs aim to address these issues with open-hardware and more secure designs, such solutions are still in development and not yet widely available.</p> <p>Unlike other privacy-preserving techniques, TEEs rely on specialized hardware features that are not universally available. This can limit their applicability and accessibility.</p> <p>TEEs are not a silver bullet for privacy and should be combined with other security measures.</p>
DP	<p>Strong privacy guarantees: Provides quantifiable bounds on privacy leakage.</p> <p>Scalable: Works well for large datasets.</p> <p>Accuracy trade-off: Introduces noise to protect privacy, potentially impacting accuracy.</p>	<p>Privacy guarantees are probabilistic, not absolute.</p> <p>Hard to implement correctly: Requires careful design and analysis.</p>
FHE	<p>Operations on encrypted data: Allows calculations on encrypted data without decryption.</p> <p>Flexible: Supports various operations and data types.</p>	<p>Computationally very expensive, slow performance.</p> <p>Some operations may introduce errors.</p>

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	<p>Strong privacy guarantees, high flexibility.</p> <p>Enables computations on outsourced data.</p>	<p>Not suitable for all types of data analysis</p>
ZKPs	<p>Prove statements without revealing underlying data.</p> <p>Used for authentication, identity verification, and secure voting.</p> <p>Offers strong privacy guarantees for specific use cases</p>	<p>Limited to specific types of statements, complex implementation.</p> <p>Can be computationally expensive for large proofs.</p>

While there is some nuance depending on application and use case, in general, the more secure the technology, the more privacy enhancing or privacy-preserving capabilities it provides.

Architectural Design Principles

- **Data minimization:** Data that is necessary for the intended purpose should be collected and stored only. Minimize the amount of sensitive data that is stored or processed.
- **Data isolation:** Sensitive data should be isolated from other systems and applications. Store and process sensitive data in a secure environment, such as a TEE or enclave.
- **Secure communication:** Secure communication channels should be used to transmit sensitive data. Encrypt data before transmitting it over networks.
- **Auditing and monitoring:** Implement auditing and monitoring mechanisms to track access to sensitive data and detect unauthorized activity.
- **Regular security reviews:** Conduct regular security reviews of systems and applications that handle sensitive data. Identify and address vulnerabilities promptly.

8.1.1 HIGH-LEVEL ARCHITECTURE BLUEPRINT

This approach provides a comprehensive framework for building secure and efficient privacy-preserving computation architectures. It combines various techniques to achieve different levels of privacy and security guarantees while considering data flow and providing suitable tools for implementation. Figure 5 provides an overview of the high-level architecture.

Figure 5: High-level architecture for privacy-preserving computation

A component description of high-level architecture for privacy-preserving computation architecture is as given below:

Data protection

Data preprocessing

Data Cleaning: Removing irrelevant or inaccurate data.

Data Aggregation: Reducing data granularity while preserving key information.

Data Sampling: Selecting a representative subset of data.

Privacy-enhancing techniques

Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE):

Traditional encryption protects data at rest and in motion but requires decryption for processing. This can be cumbersome and pose security risks.

FHE allows calculations on encrypted data, keeping it secure even when stored or processed by a third party like a cloud provider. This innovative approach:

- Guarantees data confidentiality: The data never leaves its encrypted state, even during computations.
- Empowers analysts and users: They have full access to data insights without compromising security.
- Minimizes trust reliance: Organizations can utilize third-party resources without exposing sensitive data.

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It is Ideal for:

- Cloud-based analytics: Securely leverage external computing power without compromising data privacy.
- Privacy-preserving collaborations: Enable joint analysis with partners without revealing sensitive information.
- Enhanced data security: Protect sensitive data from unauthorized access, even in complex processing environments.

What does it not protect against?

FHE presents a double-edged sword. While it enables secure data analysis, its reliance on decryption for result interpretation and its permissive nature regarding computations leave the underlying data vulnerable to unauthorized access. Anyone capable of extracting value from the results can potentially access the entire dataset, raising concerns about data privacy. Techniques such as multi-key FHE and threshold FHE solve this problem.

What are the implementation challenges?

FHE has several implementation challenges:

In situations where FHE is used to enable cloud-based analytics, there is also the question whether these computations have been done correctly.

Understanding the challenge:

Encrypted Data: In FHE, data is encrypted before being sent to the cloud. This protects privacy but makes it challenging to directly verify computation correctness on the encrypted data.

Trust in Cloud Providers: While cloud providers offer computational resources, relying solely on their assurances for correctness might not align with risk tolerance for sensitive data or critical calculations.

Solution:

Do data computation on sample data using FHE in cloud, and data computation of the sample data without FHE in the cloud. Output in both the case should be same. This will verify that computation being done in cloud is correct.

Performance:

FHE often comes with a significant performance penalty. Even the best algorithms can be several times slower than unencrypted computation, making it suitable only for a limited number of queries on small datasets.

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Storage:

Encrypted data files using FHE can be much larger than unencrypted data, leading to increased storage costs. This can negate the original benefits of utilizing FHE, which is often to leverage cloud resources for efficient processing and storage of sensitive data.

Here are some potential solutions to address this issue:

Compression techniques:

Lossless compression: Techniques like Huffman coding or dictionary-based compression can reduce ciphertext size without losing data. However, the compression ratio might be limited for specific computations.

Lossy compression: In specific scenarios, controlled lossy compression (e.g., quantization) might be acceptable if the accuracy loss does not impact the desired task.

Distributed storage:

Sharding: Splitting the ciphertext into smaller parts and storing them across multiple servers improves scalability and reduces the burden on individual storage nodes.

Cloud storage: Leveraging cloud-based storage solutions with flexible scaling and efficient data management can handle large ciphertext volumes.

Homomorphic key management:

Hierarchical key management: Using different key sizes for different levels of a computation tree can reduce the overall ciphertext size.

Key switching: Converting from one ciphertext format to another with smaller sizes can be beneficial in specific situations.

Functionality:

FHE lacks support for many standard functions, such as data transformations and joins. This limitation requires additional protocols, potentially weakening security guarantees. For example, FHE cannot perform lookups or filtering operations.

FHE schemes can evaluate any arbitrary function. In practice, evaluating non-arithmetic functions could indeed be considered challenging, but recent schemes improved the state-of-the-art significantly on that, especially for arbitrary functions with low precision. The challenge that remains is the efficient evaluation of arbitrary functions with high precision (which is currently possible, but often unpractical due to the performance overhead).

Tools: SEAL, HElib, TFHE, OpenFHE and Lattigo

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Differential Privacy (DP): Differential privacy (DP) is a rigorous mathematical framework for analysing and quantifying privacy in data analysis. It guarantees that the output of an algorithm, like a machine learning model, reveals very little information about any individual participant in the dataset, even if an attacker has access to auxiliary information.

Tools: OpenDP, TensorFlow Privacy, DpSGD, ABY3

Federated Learning (FL): Training models on local devices without sharing raw data. In federated learning (FL), multiple devices collaboratively train a model without sharing their individual data. This is a privacy-preserving approach, secure aggregation aggregates the updates from each device into a global model without revealing any individual contributions.

Secure aggregation is a cryptographic protocol that allows multiple parties to compute the sum of their private values without revealing those values to each other. In the context of FL, this means that the server can aggregate the model updates from all devices without learning anything about the individual updates or the data used to generate them. Secure aggregation is important for below mentioned reasons:

- It protects the privacy of the devices' data by preventing the server from learning anything about the individual contributions.
- It prevents malicious actors from tampering with the model updates.
- It helps to build trust in the FL process by ensuring that an adversary with access to the server is not able to unfairly influence the outcome.

How does secure aggregation work?

There are several different secure aggregation protocols, but they all share some common features. Here is a general overview of how they work:

- Each device trains a local model on its own data.
- Each device generates a model update (e.g., gradients).
- The device encrypts its update using a secure aggregation protocol.
- The encrypted updates are sent to the server.
- The server aggregates the encrypted updates using the secure aggregation protocol.
- The server decrypts the aggregated update and uses it to update the global model.

Use Case 1: Predictive airline maintenance

Each airline has its own fleet data (individual flights).

- With Secure Aggregation: FL can train a model to predict maintenance needs without revealing details about any specific flight.
- Without Secure Aggregation: An attacker could learn the airline's overall maintenance schedule, even though individual flight data is hidden.

Tools: TensorFlow Federated, PySyft, PyTorch Mobile, FATE

Secure computation

Secure Multiparty Computation (SMPC): Enables multiple parties to jointly compute a function without revealing their individual inputs.

Figure 6 illustrates the processing concept known as Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC). In the first step, the owner of a piece of data (denoted by "a") securely divides it into secret shares, represented by "x", "y", and so on. These shares are then distributed to different machines. Throughout the computation process, all data remains secret-shared, from the input shares to the output shares. Finally, the output shares can be combined to reconstruct the original result, denoted by "F(a)". [8]

Tools: SPDZ, SCALE-MAMBA, Sharemind, ABY3

Figure 6: Secure multi-party computation [7]

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Zero Knowledge Proofs (ZKPs): Allow one party to prove to another party that they possess knowledge of a secret without revealing the secret itself.

Tools: Zokrates, libsark, circom, bellman, arkworks

Secure execution environments

Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs): Hardware-based enclaves that provide a secure environment for computations to occur. Examples include Intel SGX and ARM TrustZone.

TEEs provide trusted containers for holding trusted code and data. Input is passed into the TEE over a secure channel and computation performed within the TEE, protected from the rest of the untrusted system. [9]

Figure 7: Trusted execution environment [8]

TEEs create a secure environment for code and data during execution, making them a potential alternative to cryptographic operations for protecting secrets. Intel SGX, for instance, offers secure memory enclaves where code and data reside unencrypted within the CPU's cache and registers, but remain encrypted when outside the processor. This enables faster execution within TEEs compared to slower, complex cryptographic operations. Additionally, TEEs allow verification of the contained code and data's integrity, limiting potential attacks. Ideally, an attacker could only observe resource consumption, not access the actual code or data [8].

Tools: Intel SGX SDK, ARM TrustZone CryptoCell SDK, OP-TEE

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Secure enclaves: Like TEEs, these hardware-backed enclaves offer a secure environment for sensitive operations.

Tools: Intel SGX SDK, AMD SEV, ARM TrustZone CryptoCell SDK

Hardware Security Modules (HSMs): Dedicated hardware devices designed to protect cryptographic keys and perform cryptographic operations.

Tools: Thales nShield, Yubico YubiHSM2, SafeNet Luna HSM

GPUs (Graphics Processing Units): Provide parallel processing capabilities for accelerating cryptographic operations and machine learning algorithms.

Tools: NVIDIA CUDA, AMD ROCm, TensorFlow with GPUs

FPGAs (Field-Programmable Gate Arrays): Offer hardware customization for efficient implementation of specific privacy-preserving protocols.

Tools: Xilinx Vivado Design Suite, Intel Quartus Prime Software, OpenCL

Data flow

- Data is pre-processed and transformed into a privacy-preserving format using the chosen techniques from data-protection component. Operations like encryption, decryption, and aggregation can be offloaded to GPUs or FPGAs for faster execution.
 - *Data sources:* Input data can be from various sources like sensors, user devices, or databases.
 - *Pre-processing:* Data may be pre-processed for noise addition (DP), feature extraction, or formatting for specific privacy techniques.
 - *Privacy-preserving computations:* Different techniques like FHE, DP are applied to protect data privacy during computations.
- Pre-processed data is fed for secure computations using SMPC. TEEs, and hardware acceleration are employed to achieve the desired functionality.
 - Sensitive data: Specific parts of the data flow requiring high security can be processed within TEEs or HSMs.
 - Key management: Keys used for encryption, decryption, and authentication are stored and managed securely within HSMs.
 - Secure communication: Data transfer between different layers and entities can be secured using cryptographic protocols.
 - GPUs: Provide parallel processing capabilities for accelerating computations, including encryption and decryption.

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- Operations like encryption, decryption, and aggregation can be offloaded to GPUs or FPGAs for faster execution.
- Encrypted or transformed data is processed within secure environments like TEEs or HSMs at secure execution environment.

Some other hybrid architecture blueprints are also explained below.

8.1.2 SOFTWARE-ASSISTED HARDWARE ENCRYPTION (SAHE) ARCHITECTURE

Software-Assisted Hardware Encryption (SAHE) is a security architecture that combines the strengths of software and hardware-based encryption. It uses hardware encryption engines for performing the computationally intensive encryption and decryption operations, while software handles key management, access control, and other security-related tasks.

Software-Assisted Hardware Encryption (SAHE) can be further enhanced by incorporating specialized hardware accelerators like GPUs and FPGAs. This can offer significant performance improvements and flexibility compared to traditional CPU-based encryption solutions. High-level architecture is as shown below:

Figure 8: Software Assisted Hardware Encryption architecture

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A short description of the functionality of each layer in SAHE architecture is given below:

Software stack

Data flow:

- Applications send encryption/decryption requests and data to the software stack.
- The software stack performs key management, access control, and security policy enforcement.
- Configuration management tools configure hardware resources and security policies.
- Monitoring and auditing tools gather data on system activity and potential security events.

Tools options:

- *Key management:* Keywhiz, Vault, HashiCorp Vault, Azure Key Vault, AWS KMS
- *Access control:* OPA, Gatekeeper, Keycloak, OpenID Connect, Azure Active Directory, AWS IAM
- *Security policies:* Ansible, Chef, Puppet, SaltStack, Terraform
- *Configuration management:* Ansible, Chef, Puppet, SaltStack, Terraform
- *Monitoring and auditing:* Prometheus, Grafana, Splunk, ELK Stack, Azure Monitor, AWS CloudTrail
- *API interface:* OpenAPI (Swagger), gRPC, RESTful APIs

Hardware Abstraction Layer (HAL)

Data flow:

- The software stack communicates with the HAL to access and manage hardware resources.
- The HAL translates software requests into hardware-specific commands and controls hardware resources.
- Error handling mechanisms address any issues encountered during hardware interactions.

Tools options:

- *Driver management:* Nvidia CUDA Toolkit, AMD ROCm, Xilinx SDx, Intel OpenCL
- *Resource management:* Kubernetes, Docker, Nvidia Container Toolkit, AMD ROCm Container Runtime, Intel Distribution of OpenVINO
- *Error handling:* Operating system built-in error handling mechanisms, specific hardware vendor tools
- *Performance optimization:* Nvidia Nsight Compute, AMD ROCm Profiler, Intel VTune Amplifier

Hardware acceleration engines

Data flow:

- The HAL sends encryption/decryption tasks and data to the appropriate hardware engine.
- GPU, FPGA, enclave, TEE, or HSM engines perform the designated tasks.
- Hardware engines return encrypted/decrypted data to the HAL.

Tools options:

- GPU engine: NVIDIA CUDA libraries, cuDNN, AMD ROCm libraries, HIP
- FPGA engine: Xilinx Vivado Design Suite, Intel Quartus Prime Software, OpenCL libraries
- Enclave engine: Intel SGX SDK, AMD SEV-SNP SDK, ARM TrustZone CryptoCell
- TEE engine: Apple Secure Enclave API, Trustonic TEE SDK, ARM TrustZone CryptoCell
- HSM engine: Thales nShield Connect, YubiHSM2, SafeNet Luna HSM

Application interface

Data flow:

- Applications receive encrypted/decrypted data from the software stack.
- Applications use the data for their intended purpose.

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Tools options:

- *Encryption and Decryption APIs:* OpenSSL, libsodium, BoringSSL, Microsoft CryptoAPI, AWS KMS Cryptographic SDK

Additional tools:

- *Hardware security assessment tools:* OpenSSL, Ghidra, Valgrind
- *Fuzzing tools:* AFL, libFuzzer, Honggfuzz
- *Static code analysis tools:* Coverity, SonarQube, Fortify

Choosing the right tools requires careful consideration of:

- Specific needs and requirements of the SAHE application
- Security considerations and threat model
- Performance requirements
- Budget and available resources
- Technical expertise and experience

8.2 KEY COMPONENTS OF PRIVACY-PRESERVING COMPUTATION

8.2.1 DATA PROCESSING UNITS

Hardware or software components responsible for executing secure data processing operations.

- **Secure communication channels:** Encrypted communication pathways between devices and systems.
- **Access control and authentication:** Mechanisms to authenticate users and devices and control access to resources.
- **Key management systems:** Systems responsible for generating, storing, and distributing encryption keys.
- **Audit and monitoring tools:** Tools to record and monitor security events and activities.

The data processing unit should have hardware support for TEEs. Hardware TEEs enable secure processing of data in use. The data processing unit should also have hardware support for attestation. The hardware should be able to provide an attestation report that the agent can later use in remote attestation. The attestation report is a signed binary proof that the secure TEE is indeed secure and instantiated

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correctly. In the case of Intel and AMD, the processing unit should be one of the following:

- Intel - the Intel Xeon processor with SGX support and, when available, with TDX support.
- AMD - the AMD EPYC processors with SEV/SEV-ES/SEV-SNP support.

MANAGER: software component responsible for managing and starting the secure TEEs. These TEEs can be a secure VM (AMD SEV and Intel TDX) or a secure process (Intel SGX).

AGENT: software component that will run inside the secure TEE and control the computation execution. The role of the Agent is to form a secure channel with the clients. The secure channel should be a direct secure channel with the clients; it should be established between the clients and the Agent without the interference of the hypervisor or other software on the server. The Agent is a state machine wherein, in each state, the Agent receives confidential data, receives a confidential algorithm, runs the computation, and returns the result. External clients providing confidential data and algorithms are called the data provider and algorithm provider.

These clients make the secure MPC consortium, which aims to use the data and algorithm to compute the result securely. They are expected to be bound by some internal consortium agreement regulating their rights and obligations.

The Agent software should also have all the libraries to fetch the attestation report. The secure channel is formed with each consortium member upon verifying the attestation report.

Figure 9: Attestation architecture

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Figure 10 shows the IETF RATS working group's proposed attestation architecture [10] [11]. The roles in the figure are:

- **Attester** - an entity that wants to prove its authenticity and integrity. This entity generates evidence, as shown in the figure. The evidence is the attestation report.
- **Verifier** - an entity that uses evidence and additional information to verify the attestation report (evidence) it got from the attester. It then sends the attestation results to the relying party.
- **Relying party** - the entity/client that wants to send sensitive data or code to the attester but needs assurance that the attester is secure.
- **Endorser** - an entity, typically the manufacturer, whose information (endorsements) can help verify the evidence. The endorsements are usually the information about the integrity of the evidence.
- **Reference value provider** - an entity, typically the manufacturer, which provides reference values to the verifier.
- **Verifier owner** - an entity that produces appraisal policies for evidence that the verifier uses.
- **Relying party owner** - an entity that produces appraisal policy for attestation results that the relying party uses.

The information that is being passed from one entity to another in Figure 10 is:

- **Evidence** - set of claims about the attesting environment. It contains information about the software and hardware used by the TEE. In the case of Intel and AMD, the evidence is a hardware-signed report with the mentioned information.
- **Endorsements** - represent a secure statement or a set of claims, in an open format, that some entity (e.g., a manufacturer) vouches for the integrity of the device's various capabilities.
- **Reference values** - are a set of values that represent the current "nominal values" of claims inside the evidence.
- **Attestation results** - carry information about the result of verifying the evidence. The attestation result can be a set of Boolean values about the set of claims of the evidence. The Verifier signs the attestation result for the Relying party to trust the attestation result.
- **Appraisal policies** - specify what claims in evidence or the attestation results are valid based on reference values and endorsements.

The roles defined here are not strict, and multiple entities can have numerous roles. For example, the roles of the verifier and the relying party can be unified into a

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single entity. In the case of TEEs, the attester would be the secure enclave. The endorser and reference value provider would be the hardware TEE manufacturers, for example, AMD or Intel.

The proposed attestation architecture has two models for attestation flow: the passport model and the background-check model.

The passport model (Figure 10): in this model, the attester sends the evidence to the verifier, and the verifier verifies the report and sends the attestation results back to the attester. The attester can then use the obtained evidence to provide the relying parties with proof of integrity and authenticity. Upon receiving the attestation results, the relying party should also check the attestation appraisal policy.

This verification model may fail in one of the following situations:

- The verifier may not give a positive attestation result.
- The verifier may not be accessible.
- The relying party may reject the attestation results based on the attestation result appraisal policy.

Figure 10: Passport model

The background-check model (Figure 11): in this model, the relying party receives the attestation report and sends it to the verifier. The verifier verifies the report and returns the results to the relying party. The relying party then verifies the result against its appraisal policy.

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Figure 11: Background-check model

As mentioned previously, one entity can have multiple roles. For example, the relying party and the verifier can be the same entity or on the same machine. The verification software should be transparent to the user. The details of the verification process should not burden the relying party.

Figure 12 shows the manager running on the host server and the agent running in a hardware-enabled TEE. The client, or multiple clients, can communicate with the manager using an API and a UI. The clients can create a confidential VM using the said API and boot it, as shown by the blue arrows in the figure. From there, the clients can communicate with the agent in the VM, retrieve the attestation report, and send confidential data/code if the clients successfully verify the attestation report. The purple arrows on the figure show this.

The client should have a client (guest) app installed. The guest app should be able to verify the attestation report or process the attestation results obtained from an external verifier. The verification process should include verifying the TCB version, the measurement, the signature of the trusted TEE, and all the additional data in the attestation report. The guest app should calculate the measurement of the software booted in the TEE. The measurement is successfully verified if the computed and retrieved measurements from the attestation reports match.

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Figure 12: VM flow architecture

9 TRUSTED EXECUTION ENVIRONMENTS

Protecting data at rest and in transit has been solved for quite some time using encrypted disks and secure communication channels (e.g., HTTPS). The only problem that remains is protecting the data in use. For example, if a user's application runs in the cloud, the cloud vendor or the administrator can extract the information from the application. The cloud vendor can read sensitive information from the app by examining the memory dump of the application.

Trusted execution environments (TEEs) solve this problem. TEEs provide a trusted and protected execution environment for software, often called "enclaves." The isolation and protection are guaranteed by hardware, using secure keys to encrypt/decrypt the running software. Different hardware vendors offer various solutions for TEE implementation. Most TEEs support the process of attestation. Attestation is a process in which a TEE sends cryptographic proof to a third party or another TEE to prove that it has been instantiated correctly. The attestation process aims to establish trust with a third party for that party to send confidential code or data to the TEE. This process is useful, for example, when a client does not have adequate processing power and needs to process sensitive data and, for that reason, wants to use the cloud. The client could use a hardware TEE to process his data but will need proof that the TEE has been correctly instantiated.

Intel introduced Software Guard Extensions (SGX) as a hardware TEE used to encrypt only a part of a process. The idea behind SGX is to keep the trusted computing base small to minimize the attack surface. Because SGX encrypts only a part of an application, we can divide the application into two parts: untrusted and trusted. The untrusted part is outside the TEE, and the trusted part is inside the TEE. The secure or trusted part of the application is called an enclave. When the user starts an SGX application, the enclave is loaded into a protected memory region called Enclave Page Cache (EPC) [12]. Once the enclave has been initialized, privileged code and the rest of the untrusted application cannot directly read data in the protected environment or change the code's behaviour without detection. The OS does the allocation of pages in the EPC space for enclaves. Because the OS is not trusted, the SGX processors check the correctness of the system software's allocation decisions and refuse to perform any action that would compromise SGX's security [13].

Before we talk about the attestation process of SGX, we need to talk about the provisioning process [14]. Upon installing the required software to make SGX work,

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the hardware owner needs to provision SGX. This process is performed for Intel to sign the attestation key that SGX will use to sign attestation cryptographic proof. SGX supports two types of attestation processes:

- **Local attestation** - attestation process in which one enclave establishes trust with another application on the same machine.
- **Remote attestation** - attestation process in which an enclave establishes trust with an application or a client on a different machine.

The cryptographic proof the enclave sends to the client is called the Quote [15]. The Quote contains information about the software in the enclave and the hardware on which the enclave is running. The important fields of the Quote are:

- Attributes - attributes of the enclave, such as the debug flag.
- MRENCLAVE - hash of the enclave software. A single 256-bit hash identifies the code and initial data inside the enclave. When the enclave code/data pages are placed inside the EPC, the CPU calculates the enclave measurement and stores this value in the MRENCLAVE register.
- MRSIGNER - hash of the enclave signer's key. This field is used to give information about the owner of the hardware.
- ISV SVN - security version of the enclave.

The MRENCLAVE field gives information about the code running inside the enclave. This field is essential because it convinces the client that the code inside the enclave is secure and not malicious. The client can calculate his hash and compare it with the MRENCLAVE field of the Quote. If the hashes differ, the client can abort the attestation process.

The attestation key signs the Quote. The signing is performed by an Intel architectural enclave called the Quoting enclave. This signing gives proof that the enclave is running on genuine Intel hardware.

On the other hand, AMD did not go in the direction of SGX but started by developing Secure Encrypted Virtualization (SEV) in 2016 as a technology used to encrypt whole VMs on the fly. Two more improvements were introduced to SEV by AMD, one in 2017 called SEV Encrypted State (SEV-ES) and one in 2020 called SEV Secure Nested Paging (SEV-SNP). To support SEV, AMD uses the AMD Secure processor (ASP) to safeguard all the sensitive information that needs to be kept secret for SEV to guard the VM securely [16]. ASP has been a subsystem on AMD microprocessors since 2013.

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SEV-ES provides additional security on top of SEV. One of the most notable is the encryption of the guest register state when the VM has to give control to the hypervisor. This way, a malicious hypervisor cannot use the register state to predict the code being executed in the VM.

The latest SEV iteration, SEV-SNP, has all the improvements of SEV-ES and adds [17]:

- **Memory integrity** – the integrity of the encrypted memory is protected using a new structure called Reverse Map Table (RMP) and page validation.
- **Virtual machine privilege levels (VMPL)** – SNP introduces four VMPLs (VMPL0 to VMPL3), which provide hardware-isolated abstraction layers within a VM for additional security controls. The privilege level is the highest in VMPL0 and is lower as we move towards VMPL3, where it is the lowest.
- **Interrupt/Exception protection**

All of the SEV variants support the remote attestation process, but only the SEV-SNP supports fetching the attestation report from within the VM. In the case of SEV and SEV-ES, the attestation report is fetched by the cloud provider or another software running on the same server as the confidential VM. This is achieved in SEV-SNP by creating a secure channel between the VM and the ASP firmware that is running on the AMD Secure processor.

Before analysing the attestation report of SEV-SNP, some new terms should be defined:

- **Trusted Computing Base (TCB) version** - First, the TCB of a system is a term in security architecture that refers to all the system components critical to establishing and maintaining the security of that system. The TCB version should assure the client that the server has all the latest security patches. The TCB version is information about the version numbers (or similar information) of the trusted components of the system. The firmware and software should be up to date, so the TCB version could be up to date on the host side to give maximum security to the client.
- **Measurement** - The measurement is a hash of the software inside the TEEs. The measurement should be a hash of all of the software inside the TEE, or if that is not the case, there should be a mechanism that can calculate the software's hash that is not a part of the initial measurement. For example, AMD SEV and its variants do not calculate the measurement of the whole VM but just the software present in the RAM during boot time, which is virtual machine firmware.

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- **Signature** - The hardware signs the attestation report with a chip-unique signing key or an equivalent secure key to identify the hardware. The signature validation will convince the client that the retrieved attestation report is from a VM booted on the hardware with the hardware TEE capability.

Like SGX, SEV-SNP has similar fields in the attestation report. One of the most notable are [18]:

- TCB version - a byte array containing the version numbers of all the TCB components.
- Signature algorithm - the signature algorithm used to sign the report.
- VMPL number - the VMPL number from the attestation report.
- Policy - the policy on which the VM was booted. The policy contains flags such as the debug flag.
- Report data - data that the agent can infuse into the attestation report. The agent can use this data field to send the client a public key of the agent. The public key can be trusted because it will be a part of the attestation report signed by the hardware.
- Measurement - the hash of the software that was in RAM during boot time.
- Host data - data was inserted into the attestation report by the hypervisor during the VM boot.
- Signature - the digital signature of the attestation report, created and signed by the SP firmware.

The TCB for SEV-SNP contains:

- The lowest microcode patch level of all cores.
- Version number of the SNP (ASP) firmware.
- Current ASP OS version.
- Current ASP bootloader version.

As mentioned, in the case of AMD SEV, the measurement does not contain the whole software stack's hash but only the firmware's hash. This problem can be mitigated in one of the following ways:

- Hardware measures the firmware, and then the firmware measures the rest of the software stack by emulating a virtual Trusted Platform Module (vTPM). The requirement that must be upheld is that the vTPM cannot be tampered with by the host and the guest.
- Hardware measures the firmware and the kernel. Then, the kernel measures the rest of the software stack.

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- Hardware measures the firmware, the kernel, the initrd, and the kernel command line. Then, the software part of the initrd measures the rest of the software stack. Another approach is to load the firmware, kernel, initrd, and kernel command line; by doing that, the whole software stack is part of the measurement.
- Hardware measures the entire software stack.

In 2023 Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) was introduced on Intel processors. However, there are no studies so far that analysed it in production. TDX like SEV is used to deploy hardware isolated VMs.

10 CHALLENGES (RISKS) AND ASSUMPTIONS

10.1 AMD SEV APPROACH

One of the problems faced in the experiments with AMD SEV is that the SEV calculates the measurement of the code and data that is loaded into memory during boot time, and for now, the software solutions for starting VMs, like QEMU, only load the firmware into memory during boot. This way of booting the VMs causes problems because the kernel and user space application are not part of the measurement. In other words, the agent inside the VM cannot prove to the client (third party) that the VM is properly instantiated.

10.2 EMBEDDED CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING CHALLENGES

The project aims to extend confidential computing paradigm from cloud to more constrained environments, e.g., edge devices (T3.4 Embedded Confidential Computing). This brings in many challenges. In cloud environment we can assume that computing platform is mostly Intel/AMD-based, which may have slightly different approaches to support confidential VMs, but the platforms are still sharing the same processor instruction set. Embedded Confidential Computing platforms are more heterogeneous, e.g., various ARM and RISC-V based architectures. Support for Confidential Computing practices is also less mature than in cloud-based environments.

There are also many constraints. Computing power may be limited, memory and storage space may be limited, sometimes energy consumption requires special attention. Interoperability is also a big challenge if we want to operate in heterogeneous environments. Orchestration concepts may assume deployment of computation tasks to selected available nodes or even migration of existing computing tasks. This is more challenging if we have a computing landscape that does not share the same instruction set. The project should develop mechanisms to overcome these challenges.

11 CONCLUSIONS

The document includes a list of confidential computing requirements that are collected to cover privacy-preserved computation topics and also initial use cases that are identified in the project plan. The requirements are presented using Volere template and classified to mandatory, recommended, and optional using IETF RFC 2119 terminology. These requirements are then used in CONFIDENTIAL6G technical work packages during development.

CONFIDENTIAL6G has two main approaches for privacy-preserving computation. Software-based approach is utilizing fully homomorphic encryption to protect computation and data, for example in cloud computing. Another approach relies on the use of hardware-based trusted execution environment to prevent cloud service provider to monitor or tamper sensitive data and computation. The document is describing architecture blueprints for both approaches.

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